

THE ROLE OF LINGUISTIC TOOLS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ANNOTATION

This article discusses the problems of teaching and learning a foreign language in modern times. Different approaches for teaching a foreign language, usage of different competencies, and elimination of similar problems were discussed. The role of linguistic tools in language learning is highlighted as linguistics gives language a reasonable persuasive structure when all is said and done properly.

Key words and expressions: communication, competence, pragmatics, semantics, syntax, morphology, effective didactic methods, hierarchical relation.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматриваются проблемы преподавания и изучения иностранного языка в современное время. Обсуждались разные подходы к обучению иностранному языку, использование разных компетенций и устранение сходных проблем. Подчеркивается роль лингвистических инструментов в изучении языка, поскольку лингвистика придает языку разумную убедительную структуру, когда все сказано и сделано правильно.

Ключевые слова и выражения: коммуникация, компетенция, прагматика, семантика, синтаксис, морфология, эффективные дидактические приемы, иерархическая связь.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada hozirgi zamonda chet tilini o'rgatish va o'rganish muammolari muhokama qilinadi. Chet tilini o'rgatishning turlicha yondashuvlari, turli kompetensiyalardan foydalanish va shu kabi muammolarni bartaraf etish masalalari muhokama qilindi. Shuningdek, tilni o'rganishda lingvistik vositalarning roli ta'kidlanadi, chunki tilshunoslik hamma narsa to'g'ri aytilgan va qo'llanganda tildan oqilona foydalaniladi.

Kalit so'z va iboralar: muloqot, kompetensiya, pragmatika, semantika, sintaksis, morfologiya, samarali didaktik usullar, ierarxik munosabat.

INTRODUCTION

Today, English has the largest number of native and non-native speakers in the world, and is given official language status in most countries around the world. In addition, it is being used as a teaching tool in universities among the countries of the world, where universities based on academic, political, social and economic motives are accepted as the main strategy to respond to the impact of globalization.

To this end, linguistics gives language a reasonable persuasive structure when all is said and done. It includes the following subfields: phonetics (production of speech sounds, study of acoustics and hearing), phonology (formation of sounds), morphology (structure of words), syntax (structure of sentences), semantics (meaning), pragmatics (language in context). Due to the fact that of the value and preference given to English in modern times applying it to the existing global language order, the relationship between linguistics and language teaching is described as two-way applications and influences, and the more consistent implementation of English-medium education in higher education Ethiopian universities was a possible place. The purpose of this paper is to evaluate the role of linguistics in teaching English as a foreign language.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The development of grammatical skills in foreign language communication can lead to a high level of preparation of students, which in the future will give them the

ability to competently participate in business meetings, presentations, conversations, telephone conversations. This approach involves involving the student in the language process, which provides a more natural environment for foreign language comprehension than classrooms dominated by formal grammar. Nevertheless, there is a risk that such an approach to learning a foreign language will lead to the development of a grammatically incorrect form of speech. However, in local methodological literature, the communicative approach is mainly used for the development of oral speech skills, the grammatical aspect of this approach is not clear enough. Work with students of the energy department of a non-linguistic university reliably showed that: - students have difficulties in situational use of grammatical events; - students' skills of using grammatical forms are not sufficiently formed; - Many students learned to use very simple grammatical structures in their speech, which made it difficult to use the language elements that make a foreign language sentence natural. It is possible to solve the problems that have arisen by studying the theoretical foundations related to the mechanism of formation of grammatical skills during the educational process. It is necessary to study the theoretical conditions related to the mechanism of formation of grammatical skills and qualifications. In practice, it is necessary to develop a complex of effective didactic methods of teaching communicative grammar.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study of grammar within the framework of the communicative approach led to the conclusion that grammatical phenomena are studied and acquired not as separate forms and structures, but as a set of tools for expressing certain thoughts, attitudes, communicative intentions, in the presence of linguistic and communicative competence. interconnected in the speech act. Since the main goal of language learning is communication, the studied grammatical phenomena are limited by the parameters of the situation that take into account social, semantic and discursive factors. The formation of communicative competence, which has an internal structure and includes hierarchical relations between its components, includes many aspects of linguistic knowledge, including the formation of linguistic competence, including grammatical

competence. The levels of development of communicative skills have been developed on the basis of a competence approach to learning, in accordance with the requirements set by the Council of Europe for foreign language teaching programs. The specificity of the formation of communicative grammatical skills is determined by methodological methods and tools.

The main components of this approach were the following rules: - teaching is considered as an active, conscious, creative activity; - the activity of the subject of knowledge is manifested in the educational process; - foreign language serves as a means of communication, this is its communicativeness; - learning a foreign language has a general communicative orientation, focusing on the final result; - mastering foreign language tools is aimed at their practical use in speech activity; - with the help of a foreign language, you can influence the communication partner and get information.

CONCLUSION

Linguistic culture is considered as a method of studying foreign culture through language, an important factor in educating students' feelings of citizenship, internationalism, humanity, and tolerance. In other words, foreign language teaching should be based on the developed linguistic-pedagogical model of organizing the problems of foreign language teaching and integration of cultural, personal-activity, and project approaches.

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